

Enhanced Functionality Of Fruit Yoghurt

Editorial

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Consumer's inclination towards food capable of delivering health benefits besides basic nutrition has projected the term "Functional Foods" in the world food market. Global demand for functional foods is expanding dramatically due to technological innovations, development of new products coupled with increasing consumer's consciousness about health and demand for healthy foods. Diverse factors affecting consumer's interest in functional food are increasing health care costs, increasing age of the population, the obesity epidemic, the high levels of lifestyle diseases and scientific evidence ensuring that diet can reduce diseases risk.

Recent awareness of consumers towards innovative fermented milk products containing probiotic organisms and much healthier foods coupled with documented health benefits of probiotics have led to a rapid growing interest in probiotics as functional foods in the current era of self-care and complementary medicine. Probiotics is one of the most promising functional ingredients and a diverse range of functional foods containing probiotics are available in the world market. Yoghurt being known for its health image is widely used as a probiotic carrier and their conju-

gated application result in a product with enhanced functionality and may be recommended for consumption as a dietary adjunct.

Fruit juice could be a carrier for probiotics and fermented milks incorporated with fruit matrices may be an alternative dairy product to deliver probiotic bacteria. It has been reported that yogurt containing fruit could provide probiotics, prebiotics, high-quality protein, important fatty acids and a mixture of vitamins and minerals that have the potential to exert synergistic health effects. Fruit juices may be a suitable vehicle for probiotics as it contains dietary fibres and high levels of phenolic compounds but all fruit juices are not equally suitable media for all probiotics. Various factors effecting probiotic viability in juices can be grouped as food parameters, processing parameters and microbiological parameters. Reviewed literature indicated that amongst diverse probiotics, *B. animalis* subsp. *lactis* is the most promising strain in the red-fruit juice, while *L. plantarum* c19 in apple juice. Beneficial synergistic relation between fruit and probiotic bacteria suggest their incorporation in dairy products like yoghurt and *dahi* resulting in new era in functional food innovations.

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